

LOOPER

LEARNING LOOPS IN THE PUBLIC REALM

WP4. Implementation and monitoring framework for the living labs

T4.2 Methodology and framework for monitoring and evaluation of the urban living labs

Deliverable D 4.2

FRAMEWORK FOR MONITORING AND EVALUATION OF THE LOOPER LIVING LABS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a framework for monitoring and evaluation of LOOPER (Learning Loops in the Public Realm) Urban Living Labs established in Brussels, Manchester and Verona. It is intended for use by the researchers and community partners involved in implementing the LOOPER Labs. The focus of monitoring and evaluation within LOOPER is determined by the LOOPER project objectives and the research questions derived from these, while also recognising that emphasis may be placed on different aspects within each Lab. For example, in a 'hard to reach' community, questions concerning how to engage local residents may come to the fore. Similarly, depending on the characteristics of Lab participants, different methodologies may be chosen to collect and record evaluation data. Therefore, within the framework outlined and drawing on the methodologies described, each Lab team will choose specific approaches appropriate for their local contexts and describe these in their implementation plans. A Logbook approach is proposed in order to capture the details that may help us to understand the complex processes of engagement and learning that underlie LOOPER. This can be kept in the form of a 'diary' or through completion of a series of worksheets. In both cases the same key questions must be addressed. Evaluation tasks and questions are organised within three units of analysis: (1) 'activities' (including encounters with citizens/local residents or other stakeholders; data collection activities; and any other activities related to the Lab); (2) 'stages' of the Lab cycle (or 'learning loop') and of each of the interventions tested in the final stage; and (3) the overall 'Lab' at each site and collectively.

This deliverable aims to contribute to and/or coordinate with WP2,3,4,5,6,7,8 and corresponding deliverables as follows:

- D4.1 Implementation handbook for the urban living labs (M4) (UoM)
- D5.1, D6.1, D7.1 Implementation plans for Brussels, Verona and Manchester Labs (VUB, IUAV, UoM) (M5)
- Reports from each Lab on all stages
- D5.4, D6.4, D7.4 Evaluation reports including learning outcomes and policy transfer from Brussels, Verona and Manchester Labs (VUB, IUAV, UoM) (M32)
- D2.1 Report on data collection procedure framework (M3) (IUAV)
- D3.1 Guidelines for the co-design of alternative solutions (M4) (VUB)
- D3.2 Report on the methodology to include hard-to-reach groups (M7) (VUB)
- D3.3 Report on the specifications for integrating evaluation tools in the LOOPER platform (M10) (VUB)
- D3.4 Scientific publication on the integration of evaluation tools into the co-creation process (M35) (VUB)
- D8.1 Learning loop synthesis report and guidelines for the future application of the LOOPER methodology in living labs (M35) (UoM)
- D8.3 Synthesis for policy makers report (M33) (UoM)

I. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this document is to set out monitoring and evaluation guidelines for the LOOPER Urban Living Labs established in Brussels, Manchester and Verona. The central goal of LOOPER is to ‘demonstrate learning loops in the public realm’. Our monitoring and evaluation framework should support us in determining whether our learning loop approach is effective in addressing problems in the public realm, and what it is about the approach that makes it more or less effective. We therefore want to assess impacts in terms of addressing identified problems and also to analyse the learning processes which are at the core of the LOOPER approach. The monitoring and evaluation process should itself contribute to the learning process for those implementing and participating in the Labs with learning feeding into how we undertake our next stages of work. This is usually described as formative evaluation as mentioned in section II.a below.

Evaluation processes are guided by evaluation questions. In the case of a research project like LOOPER evaluation questions should be formulated based on the objectives and research questions of the project, which are laid out in II.c, and adapted for each Lab in accordance with the characteristics of the place and problems to be addressed. Evaluation questions can be answered using a range of methodologies as described in II.d with the qualitative data recorded in a logbook or similar format with the capacity to capture detail. The evaluation framework adopts three units of analysis: (1) ‘activities’ (including encounters with citizens/local residents or other stakeholders; data collection activities; and any other activities related to the Lab); (2) ‘stages’ of the Lab cycle (or ‘learning loop’) and of each of the interventions tested in the final stage; and (3) the overall ‘Lab’ and its impact on the neighbourhood, on policy, and on other stakeholders. A description of tasks to be carried out for each unit of analysis is provided, accompanied by worksheets containing corresponding evaluation questions in an appendix.

II. SETTING UP THE MONITORING AND EVALUATION PROCESS¹

a. Formative and Summative Evaluation

As stipulated for WP4, both formative and summative evaluation of LOOPER Labs should be undertaken. ‘*Formative* evaluation uses evaluation methods to improve the way a program is delivered. At the other end of this continuum is *summative* evaluation, which measures program outcomes and impacts.’ (Newcomer et al., p. 8)

In the case of LOOPER we will use formative evaluation (often through informal discussions within teams, which may be captured through keeping a log) to answer questions like: Are our approaches to engaging local residents effective? Our answers to these questions will guide our subsequent actions

¹ The terms ‘monitoring’ and ‘evaluation’ are used in different contexts in this document: The ‘evaluation of possible solutions’ with MCA or MAMCA is different from the wider ‘evaluation of learning, process and outcomes’ which is the primary subject of this document. Similarly ‘monitoring’ is also used in the citizen monitoring/participatory sensing context. Monitoring means to observe and check the progress or quality of something over a period of time and ‘Monitoring and Evaluation’ is the standard vocabulary for describing a key component of organisational and programme/project management

i.e. we will continue using approaches that we have seen to be successful and change those that are not. Our summative evaluation is where we will ‘sum it all up’ at the end of our project based on data collected throughout all the stages of our Labs. We will complete our analysis of the quantitative and qualitative data that has been collected from the Labs overall in order to answer the evaluation questions we have set ourselves—and consequently the related research questions (see below). The summative evaluation should also help us to decide if the LOOPER model can be usefully applied again by ourselves or others. If we conclude that the LOOPER model is worthy of dissemination, the summative evaluation will be an important tool in promoting it.

b. Get ready to be a Researcher in your own project

One way to understand LOOPER is as a controlled experiment: “We shall set up a Living Lab, and if we improve the traffic safety in our neighbourhood, the format of Living Labs works well! If we do not improve traffic safety, the Living Lab was not a good format for our circumstances.” If this was the only question to answer, it would be enough to check at the very end of the three years.

But there are so many insights we would lose on the way if we only focused on that. What about these questions?

- Why did nobody come to our meetings?
- Why did our meetings not attract a diverse crowd of people?
- Why did the relationship between city and citizens remain very conflictual?
- Why did we actually succeed in coming to a consensual solution in our Living Lab?
- How did people’s understanding of air quality measures change through the project?

To find answers to these questions, we need to look for cause and effect (e.g. Cause: We promoted our events in a way that many people did not feel personally addressed. Effect: Nobody came) or changes over time (e.g. we have quotes from citizens about air quality measures throughout a period of three years).

In order for us to discover these potential cause and effect relations or changes over time, we need to frame evaluation questions and collect data, including through regularly taking notes about what is occurring in our Labs. These notes can be messy, they can be voice recordings, they can be in our mother tongue, everything is suitable. Plus, we can take the time to write down anything else that surprises us! These notes will allow us to be open to new findings which we could not have expected in advance. These notes will be of great value after the three years when someone in the research team will look back and, among other things, make comparisons between the living labs.

This evaluation should, as far as possible, be co-produced, i.e. discussed with the researchers, community and policymakers/professionals. It will need to be put into appropriate language to communicate with the co-producers. Co-producing the evaluation means: (1) telling Lab participants what questions we are trying to answer and asking them if they have related questions they would like answered; (2) asking Lab participants for advice on how to answer these questions in the context of the place they live or work i.e. about what methods we should use to collect data for the evaluation; (3) asking Lab participants to participate in evaluation activities such as questionnaires, interviews, focus groups; (4) discussing and reflecting on evaluation findings with Lab participants throughout the process; and (5) sharing the initial conclusions of the evaluation with Lab participants in order to receive and incorporate their feedback.

c. Get to know the key research questions (and determine relevant evaluation questions)

Monitoring and evaluation of the Looper Living Labs should be framed by the project objectives and research questions. The research questions should guide the development of our evaluation questions because the evaluation questions will contribute to answering the research questions. At the same time, we should remain open to modifying our research questions and our evaluation questions or adding new ones as we move through our learning loops. We should also bear in mind that certain

research questions may be more relevant for certain Labs and the research interests of the researchers involved. Each Lab team should review the research questions and identify those most relevant to them (and add additional questions if required) and then rephrase these questions in a way that makes sense to them (as some of the below questions have already been rephrased by different people). These questions should be listed in the evaluation section of our implementation plans. These can then guide development of evaluation questions for the specific Lab.

There is a difference between research questions and evaluation questions. Research questions guide research. They can be answered by drawing on a range of sources including research carried out by others. Evaluation questions seek to understand what happens within a particular project or activity in order to determine its value and significance. The answers to evaluation questions can contribute to answering research questions.

The following objectives (in bold) are based on the original LOOPER proposal. They are followed by sets of research questions.

Project objectives and research questions fully covered in this document

1. **Demonstrate the ‘learning loop’ principle enhanced by smart technology.** A learning loop is a process of reflection-action-reflection. The LOOPER approach enhances this process by (a) seeking to involve all key actors (citizens, stakeholders, policymakers) in learning; (b) enriching learning through data collection and visualisation by the key actors; (c) extending co-creation to the full planning cycle; and (d) including a second learning loop where learning from the first can be applied and interventions refined.

The related research questions are as follows, and also include some of those listed in relation to other objectives.

- What is the value added of involving all of these actors in the process?
- What are the most effective ways of engaging the relevant actors?
- Is the enhanced learning loop approach an effective way to address problems in the public realm?

2. **Produce guidelines for the translation of the raw information from participatory data collection into validated and useful knowledge for stakeholders through visualisation.**

The related research questions are:

- How can participatory sensing/citizen monitoring² combine with deliberation to identify and understand problems in the urban environment?
- How can citizen monitoring be combined with deliberation to assist in co-design for solutions in the urban environment?
- How can co-creation processes be improved through a better visualisation and dissemination of participatory data for citizens and explain how citizens perceive urban issues?

Research question covered briefly in section 2.5 and more deeply in D3.3

3. **Develop a methodology to link participatory data collection and co-designed alternatives to formal quantitative evaluation methods (Multi-Criteria and Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis [MAMCA]) to improve the feasibility of implementation and ensure the support of decision makers.**

The related research questions are:

- How can citizen monitoring and co-design enhance the use of MCA and MAMCA?

² Participatory sensing (which is particularly associated with mobile devices and online platforms) and citizen monitoring have similar but slightly different meanings. The former is used in the LOOPER funding proposal and both are used in LOOPER deliverables.

- How can MCA and MAMCA enhance citizen monitoring and co-design?

Research questions covered in WP8

These questions will be dealt with in Work Package 8, Task 8.3 (Policy recommendations, outreach to policy makers). A Synthesis for Policy Makers report will be produced in English and three other languages, with supporting brochure. This will contain policy recommendations at multiple levels, practical methods and tools, and a summary of the living lab experience in the following deliverables:

- D8.1 Learning loop synthesis report and guidelines for the future application of the LOOPER methodology in living labs (M35)
- D8.3 Synthesis report for policy makers (M33) (UoM)
- D8.4 Policy recommendations brochures in local languages (M34) (UoM)

4. **Demonstrate and compare how citizens and other stakeholders can gain environmental, social and economic benefits from a fully participatory (see Arnstein's [1969] ladder of participation) co-creation process in three urban living labs with different spatial, cultural and thematic contexts.**

The related research questions are:

- How can policy learning enhance citizen co-design?
- How does data visualisation and analysis enhance citizen co-design?
- What is the influence of governance structure and participation culture on co-creation based on the comparison of empirical evidence from the living labs?
- How do the differences in legal and regulatory systems (e.g. on data protection) influence the feasibility and the outcome of the different phases of co-creation?

5. **Produce a set of recommendations for civil organisations and local authorities to develop learning loops of co-creation to address conflicts and mobilise synergies in the public realm.**

The related research questions are:

- How can the overall results contribute to community learning and development? How can the overall results contribute to policy learning and development? How can the findings from the urban living labs inform policies through and enhance the practice of citizen participation?

6. **Advance the knowledge of urban practitioners on how smart participatory processes that include multi-domain aspects and a combination of traditional and online participatory tools can improve urban planning and design processes.**

The related research questions are:

- How can policy benefit from citizen monitoring and co-design?
- How can quantitative data link with qualitative data to enhance co-design and implementation?
- What are the conditions for linking up qualitative and quantitative tools across the full planning cycle?
- How can online tools link with off-line tools to enhance co-design and implementation?
- How can a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies as well as online and offline tools realise an inclusive planning process?

d. How to gather the information

Data collection methods and tools should be chosen for the evaluations. There are various options and each Lab team can decide which are most practical and suitable, for example:

- Quantitative measurements of defined indicators
- Surveys (online or offline)

- Interviews (structured or semi-structured) with selected residents or stakeholders
- Participant diaries or online comments
- Focus groups, small group discussions
- Include a regular evaluation item in general discussions or meetings (this may be the most practical where time and resources are scarce)

Quantitative data plays an important role in the LOOPER process and detailed instructions for quantitative measurements (of air quality, noise, traffic speed) are provided in D2.1 Report on data collection procedure framework (M3) (IUAV). Quantitative data can function as “proof” to convince decision-makers. It can strengthen conclusions. However, many details and potential conclusions will not be measurable. Even if something is not measurable, it might still be there. Plus, the attempt to quantitatively measure something might be so resource-intensive, that other details are neglected. Plus, it is good to be able to put the measurements in context! For that **we also need qualitative data** like quotes and notes from interviews, observations, etc. to deepen our analysis and to strengthen and illustrate our conclusions.

Gathering quantitative data

Find measurable indicators for your Lab’s objectives and monitor these indicators throughout the Lab (you can set targets for success or not). **These should be included in our implementation plans.**

Examples:

- Participant numbers in activities – indicating effectiveness of specific outreach approaches and/or the level of interest in specific activities. This can also be used as a starting point for an analysis of the contribution of each stage or set of activities to the effectiveness of the overall LOOPER approach.
- Number and timing of activities attended by an individual – indicating participation patterns of individuals e.g. whether they consistently participate in LOOPER activities or only in certain types or drop out after a certain time. The reasons behind this can then further explored.

Keep it simple, there is not always a need for long questionnaires. In many cases an interview can deliver much richer data.

Gathering qualitative data

A case study approach: The evaluation of each lab is essentially a case study. We will analyse what occurs within each case and compare the cases. A case study approach is appropriate because our research questions are primarily ‘how’ questions (Yin, 2009, pp. 8–9) We are trying to understand how things work in a LOOPER Lab. Case studies are well suited to seeking answers to these questions because of the opportunities they provide for in-depth description of social phenomena within a real life context (Yin, 2009).

Personal accounts are key when working on case study research. When writing about what we observed in the Labs, we will sometimes be unable to support our impressions and claims with numbers, due to the small scale. Instead, we can illustrate our claims through quotes that exemplify a given observation.

There are four common qualitative data collection methods: (1) **Observation** is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviours in particular contexts. Participant observation, where the researcher is a participant in the situation being observed, is most appropriate for our Labs. (2) **Interviews**, which may be structured, semi-structured or unstructured. Semi-structured interviews are likely to be most useful in the LOOPER context. These involve questions that are pre-determined by the researcher but remain open. This allows participants to respond in their own ways and emphasise the things they feel to be important. The interviewer also maintains the flexibility to pose some additional or different questions in order to pursue lines of inquiry opened up by the respondent (Longhurst, 2009). In-depth interviews are optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being

explored. Non-numerical surveys or questionnaires can serve similar functions to structured or semi-structured interviews. (3) **Focus groups**, where multiple participants discuss a question or an issue, are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. (4) **Use of secondary data**, which can include diaries, news reports, records of meetings or events, photographs. In all of these cases, noting down full quotes is very valuable. Making audio recordings of interviews and focus group is extremely useful if participants consent to this, not least because we sometimes do not realise which data is important until later on in the research or evaluation process.

Some potential tools for our Labs are described below. Each Lab team will need to select and adapt tools that are appropriate to its particular activities and the participants involved.

Participant Diaries – equivalent to semi-structured questionnaires or interviews

Participant diaries are a useful tool in qualitative research and evaluation (Lewis et al., 2005) Within the LOOPER labs we could prepare diaries with question prompts for participants (drawn from worksheets 1.4 and 1.5) to fill in throughout the LOOPER process. Depending on how this is set up, it may or may not work. If it is a nice little booklet and people are free to choose whether to take one, it should work fine. (As we are guiding the content of the diaries, this would be considered more of a questionnaire than secondary data.)

With the same question prompts in mind, small talk after an event could fulfil the same purpose, basically letting researchers do mini-interviews with a few individuals per event.

Further reading: <https://www.quirkos.com/blog/post/qualitative-participant-diaries>

Learning Self-Assessments – open-ended (semi-structured) interviews

We suggest a representative sample of participants should be asked to complete a learning self-assessment which can then inform the overall evaluation. The self-assessment is probably best done verbally in an informal open-ended interview, based on learning-related questions selected from the evaluation questions such as those in Sheet 1.4

Workshop leader observations

Your anecdotes are important. After a meeting, use the evaluation questions as inspiration to note down anything that: was remarkable, worried you, you noticed in the behaviour of participants.

Sit down directly after a given event and note your impressions. What you find surprising, unexpected, uncomfortable, exciting... is relevant! Still, the evaluation questions listed in this document may point you to concrete things to look out for (see Sheets 1.4 and 1.5).

A simple yet rich way would be to create an audio recording of yourself. Audio diaries to both record your personal learning, as well as the impressions you gathered from interactions with other participants. You can of course also directly type up your impressions.

Focus group – small group discussion

Organising a focus group involves inviting a selected group of people to participate in a facilitated discussion about questions or issues chosen by the researchers. They often involve selecting people who are part of a particular group whose shared perspectives the researcher hopes to better understand. Focus groups may therefore be useful in our Labs to get an understanding of the views of different groups of stakeholders or of people who participated in a particular LOOPER activity. Focus groups are also useful because people often feed off one another's ideas, which may produce a richer discussion. However, this will only happen if the discussion is not dominated by one or two individuals and it is the role of the focus group facilitator to ensure this does not happen. The facilitator also asks questions to start the discussion (or section of the discussion) and manages the time to ensure that all the questions are covered, and encourages the participants to stay on topic. If audio recording is not

possible, a note taker should be present to record the discussion. This would be appropriate at milestones of the project, i.e. the completion of the data collection phase (see Sheet 2.3).

External Sources (secondary data)

Things that are already written on paper can also be valuable. This may involve monitoring press releases around the topic or language used by public officials in their e-mails.

e. The LOOPER Lab Logbook

The simplest way to assemble the information we hope to gather is in a logbook where we record our Lab activities. (Note that this logbook will serve as a bank of information throughout the project, which can be used for many purposes, not just evaluation.) A 'logbook' or 'log' is a record of events usually dated and arranged chronologically. Logs are used in a variety of contexts including laboratories where researchers usually record procedures and results, as well as their own observations. The log can be thought of as a 'scientific diary' and like participant diaries it is an effective way to capture important detail for evaluations (Cohen et al., 2006). The logbook should be a continuous record of the events that form part of an experiment, and of the researchers' reflections on these events. The notes should be entered as soon as possible after the event has occurred so that details can be recalled, and feelings and observations captured. For evaluation purposes, providing details about what is being evaluated allows for more in-depth evaluation. We are more likely to know why something was successful or not if we have information about exactly how the activity unfolded.

The logbook can be considered a monitoring tool in the monitoring and evaluation of our LOOPER Labs. You should therefore consider the evaluation questions listed in the annexes when reflecting on the events described in your log i.e. you should pose the questions to the data and record the answers that the data provides (in the logbook itself or in the attached worksheets). Inserting the evaluation questions into the document where we record the details of our actions and observations may also help us to keep an eye out for what is relevant to record at that moment. The evaluation questions should stimulate thinking about what we are learning as we go along, and as a result the log will become a formative evaluation as well as a monitoring tool. Lab teams should take the time to discuss what has been recorded in the logbook at each step and adjust their approaches in subsequent steps if required.

An advantage of keeping a log is that it will allow us to accumulate rich content, which can be analysed and used to produce a range of different documents such as guidelines, reports, journal articles, i.e. our 'deliverables'. It is suggested that you organise your logbook according to the section headings in the outline that follows. Ideally, when it is time for one of the project reports to be submitted, you can copy and paste together the relevant sections from your logbook and write introduction, conclusion, etc. to go with it.

f. Units of analysis and organisation of evaluation tasks and questions

It is common within evaluation processes to evaluate things at different levels or using different lenses and combine the findings to create a more complete picture of what is being evaluated. Our units of analysis are: (1) 'activities' (including encounters with citizens/local residents or other stakeholders; data collection activities; and any other activities related to the Lab); (2) 'stages' of the Lab cycle (or 'learning loop') and of each of the interventions tested in the final stage; and (3) the overall 'Lab' at each site and collectively. Evaluation tasks and questions are organised by unit of analysis into three parts within the following outline and the corresponding worksheets.

1. EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH LAB ACTIVITY

The **first unit of analysis is the activity**, and particularly important among our activities are the encounters with local residents and other stakeholders. These may be brief informal encounters or well prepared LOOPER workshops or participatory sensing campaigns. All should be captured in the Lab Log but some with a paragraph and others taking up multiple pages. Taking detailed notes before and after each encounter or other activity is time-intensive but allows us to both be well-prepared and look back months later and understand changes over time. In these notes you should attempt to capture the experiences of both activity organisers and participants.

This first unit of analysis is broken down into three sections: tracking activities overall; pre-meeting (or other significant activity); and post-meeting (or other significant activity). Templates are provided to organise this information as outlined below.

1.1. Tracking activities

(by lab coordinator)

Use this table to track your key activities (e.g. workshops, data collection campaigns, other encounters). Include dates, content and key results. Note anything that you find relevant and want to highlight.

See [Sheet 1.1](#) for the table to be completed. You should prepare one table for the whole Lab or if you prefer, you could have one for each type of activity (e.g. meetings, participatory sensing).

1.2. Pre-Meeting

(by lab coordinator)

Define the purpose of the meeting or other event. Note down which activities you intend to undertake with participants. Then plan your time. You should do this for each significant event.

1.2.1 Setting structure and purpose

(by lab coordinator; make sure to share this with participants at the beginning of the meeting. Be transparent about the structure and purpose of everything)

Resource: <http://toolbox.hyperisland.com/idoarrt-meeting-design>

Address the following questions and record your responses in [Sheet 1.2](#).

- **Intention** – What is the intention, or purpose, of the meeting? In other words, why have it?
- **Desired Outcome(s)** – What specific outcomes should be achieved by the end of the meeting?
- **Agenda** – What activities will the group go through, in what order, to move toward the desired outcome?
- **Roles** – What roles or responsibilities need to be in place for the meeting to run smoothly? Who is facilitating, and who is participating? Who is documenting, and who is keeping track of the time? What do you expect of the participants?
- **Rules** – What guidelines will be in place during the meeting? These could relate to agreed group norms. They could also relate to use of laptops/mobiles, or practical rules related to a space. Let the participants add rules to ensure that they have ownership of them.

- **Time** – What is the expected time for the meeting, including breaks, and at what time will the meeting end?

1.2.2 Developing activities

(by lab coordinator)

Choose or design specific activities that you will use during your events. The below example from the Brussels Lab is an activity to discuss what the Lab is trying to measure and what data needs to be collected over a series of months. You can find more examples of workshop activities and tools at <https://seedsforchange.org.uk/tools.pdf>. You should write a description (or copy the description from its source) for each activity you use in your Lab.

Example activity: ‘What to measure in order to do what?’

- Make small groups of 2-5. Give each group a poster like the one shown below, some post-its and some felt pens.
- Give the groups 50 minutes to populate their timelines with concrete ideas written on post-its.
- Present an exhibition where everyone stands around each poster and one of the group members introduces the key ideas generated by his or her group. Invite members of other groups to ask questions or comment.

Figure 1 Material used in an example activity

1.2.3 Create Workshop Plan

(by lab coordinator)

Prepare a schedule for your workshop or other event with responsibility allocated and materials required for different activities.

Enter this information into the table in [Sheet 1.3](#).

1.3. Post-Meeting

The pre-meeting notes record what we did or tried to do while the post-meeting notes record the response to the meeting (or other event). For each meeting or event we organise, we should attempt to gather feedback from participants regarding their feelings about the event and the effect that it had on

them. We should also reflect as a Lab team (ideally with some of the participants) on how this event contributes to the development of the Lab (e.g. engages people and/or prepares them next for next stages, provides orientation for what we should do next).

1.3.1 Feedback

(by lab coordinator involving full group)

As the last point of the event, ask for feedback:

- Go around the group, each person says one thing that they learned or liked about today and one suggestion for improvement as things go forward
- Have someone (e.g. researcher) record the responses and discuss these afterward among the Lab team and decide how to adjust approaches

For engaging feedback methods, see:

<https://woodcraft.org.uk//sites/default/files/Evaluation%20and%20reflection%20activities.pdf>

(these are posted by an organisation working with children and youth but should work just as well with adults)

1.3.2 Asking participants

(by lab coordinator or researcher involving some participants)

The lab coordinator and/or researcher informally asks participants questions about their experience of the event either one-on-one or in small groups as the event breaks up. Then the coordinator/researcher will have to write the answers down from memory after the event.

See [Sheet 1.4](#) for the questions to be answered.

1.3.3 Reflections

(by lab coordinator and researcher potentially involving participants)

After each meeting, record what your group discovered and map your progress as you go forward. Reflect on what you did, what you learned and what you are going to do next. Reflecting on these questions may be a bit time intensive and not feasible with the whole group. (Although these questions might come up during the meeting itself-and responses should be noted.) See whether you can do this with one or two citizens or if lab coordinator and researcher can do this together.

See [Sheet 1.5](#) for the questions to be answered.

1.3.4 Immediate Follow-Up

(by lab coordinator, engaged citizens, potentially researcher)

It is important to take the momentum of the meeting forward and follow-up immediately. Give the impression of something meaningful happening. Don't let the energy from the meeting fizzle out. Record what you do and any effects that it has.

See [Sheet 1.6](#) for the table to be completed.

1.4. "Primary Sources" for each meeting

(by researcher, maybe with the help of the lab coordinator forwarding information)

Collect and conserve any materials related to the meeting. This material allows a third person to analyse, for example, how the tone of communication might have changed or not changed. Coordination e-mails may give further insights into why you decided to do something. Relevant materials include:

- Press Releases
- E-mails sent to participants
- E-mails for coordination
- Published Blog posts afterwards

2. EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

2.1. Lab Set Up

Our labs were established with a pre-determined purpose and structure as defined in the funding proposal. Therefore, we did not need to start with a workshop to define these as is suggested for example in the Urban Living Lab Kit 'Urban Lab in a day' guidelines (<http://www.urbanexp.eu/labkit>) (Scholl et al., 2017) The process of setting up the Labs varied across the three sites and we have not defined very specific evaluation questions relevant to this stage. However, a brief description of the process and reflections on how it went and possible lessons learned would be useful.

2.1.1 Reflection on setting up the Lab

Reflect on how the process of setting up the lab went and how it might be improved if you were to do it again. See [Sheet 2.1](#) for the questions to be answered.

2.1.2 Preparing to evaluate learning through the LOOPER stages

There are two preliminary questions about learning to be answered toward the beginning of each LOOPER Lab and revisited at the end of the project (See [Sheet 2.1](#)). These will help you to define which sorts of learning involving which learners are needed to achieve the LOOPER goals of improving decision making/co-creation and addressing problems in the public realm.

Examples of different sorts of learning:

- Skills e.g. listening, communicating, data collection, problem-solving, networking
- Knowledge e.g. awareness of shared neighbourhood concerns; understanding of relevant issues; understanding of institutions and procedures
- Attributes e.g. confidence, openness to perspectives of others, creativity

Examples of learners:

- Individuals? Groups? Organisations?
- Local residents (particular demographics?)
- Community Organisations
- Local government
- National Government
- Business
- Planners, Engineers, Landscapers
- Academics

2.1.3 Questions to be asked at every LOOPER stage

On some aspects we should keep a constant eye. These include learning, the usage of online tools and the general mood among Lab participants. Researchers/lab coordinators can take a look at these questions in [Sheet 2.1](#) as you move from one stage to the next and see which of them evoke a reaction. Write down whatever seems relevant. You don't know the answer to many of these? Maybe it is time

to call up one of your citizens or partner organisations and ask them about these things. They are surely happy to be asked about their impressions.

2.1.3.1 Learning

The questions in [Sheet 2.1](#) about the learning taking place at each stage should be answered in light of the responses in section 2.1.2 (preparing to evaluate learning). Having identified who needs to learn what, we are now trying to determine if we have created opportunities for participants to learn what is needed to achieve the LOOPER goals of improving decision making/co-creation and addressing problems in the public realm.

In order to determine what and how people are learning, we should choose one or more methods described earlier in this document i.e. participant diaries, self-assessments, interviews and/or observation.

Examples of how people may be learning:

- Through social learning where individuals share their own perspectives and co-construct an understanding of the situation³
- Through exchanges where they articulate, clarify and adjust their understanding
- Through sharing what they have learned with other with others
- Learning by doing; hands on activities
- Using online or offline tools
- Being provided with data in simple statements e.g. average PM of x (acceptable level is y)
- Through data visualisation
- Through stories or testimonies describing how people in the neighbourhood are affected
- Through personal experiences of monitoring/collecting data

2.1.3.2 Use of online tools?

Assessing the role of online tools in participatory processes is a key objective of LOOPER. It is therefore essential to gather information about the interest and capacity of participants to access and to use online tools—and to note any effects that use of online tools has on learning and action within LOOPER. See [Sheet 2.1](#) and Sheet 2.3 for the questions to be answered.

2.1.3.3 General mood amongst lab participants?

In addition to learning and engaging with online tools, it is important to note (see [Sheet 2.1](#)) how participants are engaging with the LOOPER process overall. This may yield insights that may otherwise be overlooked. Paying attention to how participants are feeling is also important in our formative evaluation process and should orient our next steps.

2.2.Scoping

The scoping stage serves to identify affected communities and the problems that affect them. The Lab team reaches out to local residents and other stakeholders and attempts to engage them in a process of deliberation about key problems in the public realm of the designated area. Monitoring and evaluation at this stage focus on determining whether we have reached the necessary people and

³ Social learning is the collective learning through action and reflection that results in enhancing a group's ability to change its underlying dynamics and assumptions (Tippett & Searle 2005). See also Keen et al., *Social Learning in Environmental Management: towards a sustainable future*.

assessing the effectiveness of our approaches to engaging them and facilitating identification of problems. A list of the problems identified should be included along with comments about any difficulties or conflicts that emerged in the deliberation process and how these were, or were not, resolved. As in other evaluation tasks, the evaluation will be enriched by detailed notes about what we did and what we observed combined with reflections from the Lab team and participants (gathered through interviews or participant diaries). This process should be undertaken for both the first and second learning loops. See [Sheet 2.2](#) for the questions to be answered concerning engagement and problem and problem identification.

2.3.Data Collection and Visualisation

See [Sheet 2.3](#) for the questions to be answered.

2.3.1 Pre-Data Collection

The LOOPER project seeks to investigate the effect of participatory data collection on understanding, deliberation and action in relation to local problems. We must therefore monitor the quality of group debate before participatory data collection is undertaken in order to compare it with quality of debate post-data collection. This includes noting observations about how people talk about problems, how they determine *the* problem, and how they support their opinions (e.g. quantitative data; their personal experience; what they read in the newspaper or online; what they hear others say). It is also important to note citizens' expectations concerning data collection and then later to see if these are met. The questions in [Sheet 2.3](#) should be answered using information gathered through observation and interviews with participants.

2.3.2 Post-Data Collection

During and after the participatory data collection, the same methods should be used to answer similar questions geared to tracking changes in how participants understand and discuss the identified problems. Participants' experience of undertaking data collection should also be recorded in accordance with the questions in [Sheet 2.3](#). As in previous stages, detailed recording of what happened during the data collection stage will lead to richer analysis

2.3.3 Post-Visualisation

In the next stage the data collected is translated into formats that make it more understandable and meaningful. This process of visualisation facilitates the communication of information about local problems back to the citizenry and to other stakeholders. At this stage our monitoring and evaluation efforts are focused on describing and assessing the process and products of visualisation and the effects that it has on understanding and action—in particular about whether it prepares participants for co-design of effective solutions and mobilisation in support of these. See the last section of [Sheet 2.3](#) for the questions to be answered.

2.4.Co-design

Participants who have engaged in some or all previous stages of LOOPER (problem identification, data collection, visualisation) are now invited to engage in co-design of solutions to the problems they have identified and learned more about. Other stakeholders who are completely new to LOOPER are also welcome to participate in the co-design process. This provides us with an opportunity to explore how different journeys through the LOOPER stages by different people have prepared them to play a role in co-design, and to assess the effects of their participation on themselves and also on the co-design process and outcomes. It would be appropriate at this stage to conduct some in-depth interviews with people who are exemplars of different levels of engagement with LOOPER.

This stage is also an opportunity to test different co-design tools, both online and offline. As a result we should be describing and evaluating the co-design process in the same way as that used for all activities/events (see Section 1) and remembering to assess learning and online experience as relevant to each stage (see Section 2.1.2).

All of the Labs are being equipped with an online co-design platform (using the Nextseventeen co-creative Wordpress theme from Nexthamburg) and we must monitor its use and outcomes. Each Lab team will also choose or develop other co-design tools or approaches that are relevant to the context of their labs and it is important that the different co-design processes are described in detail so that is clear to all what is being assessed.

See [Sheet 2.4](#) for the questions to be answered pre- and post- co-design.

2.5.Evaluation of possible solutions

One of the LOOPER objectives is to develop a methodology to link participatory data collection and co-designed alternatives to formal quantitative evaluation methods (Multi-Criteria Analysis [MCA] and Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis [MAMCA]) to improve the feasibility of implementation and ensure the support of decision makers.

Through our monitoring and evaluation, we want to find out if and how MCA and MAMCA can enhance participatory data collection and co-design. LOOPER also seeks to understand if participatory data collection and co-designed alternatives enhance MCA and MAMCA, which is an area of enquiry that will need to be undertaken by the Brussels team members who have experience of their use in other contexts. Detailed guidelines will be developed in the framework of “D3.3 Linking co-design with evaluation”.

MCA and MAMCA can be used online and/or in workshop format. Depending on how we use them, we should be describing and evaluating the process in the same way as that used for all activities/events (see Section 1) and remembering to assess learning and online experience as relevant to each stage (see Section 2.1.2).

This stage of LOOPER will involve existing and new participants in the LOOPER process and we should pay close attention to how they are brought into the process, the roles they play and the interaction among them. This will allow us to observe whether previous participants welcome or resent/reject the introduction of new criteria and new actors. It may demonstrate that local residents have developed confidence in their capacity as local experts vis-à-vis professional actors or that the MCA/MAMCA process serves to undermine them. We can explore what trade offs, if any, must be made in order to increase feasibility and decision makers’ support.

See [Sheet 2.5](#) for the questions to be answered at the stages of pre- and post-evaluation of possible solutions.

2.6.Implementation of interventions and monitoring plans

Having identified the one, two or three interventions to be tested, we now seek to implement them with the same emphasis on the importance of stakeholder participation, and on how this participation supports learning and action. Our monitoring and evaluation thus continues to focus on these aspects, but at this stage it is also concerned with assessing the effectiveness of each intervention in order to demonstrate potential solutions for the identified problems.

See [Sheet 2.6](#) for the questions to be answered.

2.6.1 Pre-implementation

2.6.1.1 Description of the intervention

We begin with a description of the intervention to be implemented. If more than one intervention is planned, please complete a separate worksheet ([Sheet 2.6](#)) for each intervention beginning with its title, a photo and a brief description. Basic information should be provided about the intervention in accordance with the questions in [Sheet 2.6](#). The response to the first question, 'What is the intervention?', should describe the physical or social changes that are being made. In keeping with the LOOPER emphasis on participation, all partners in the intervention should be listed along with their role (e.g. coordination, hosting, expertise, monitoring) and any resources they contribute (either monetary or in-kind).

2.6.1.2 Monitoring plan

As we are implementing these interventions in order to test them, monitoring of the results is key and a monitoring plan should be developed for each intervention in accordance with the questions in [Sheet 2.6](#). It should include the following information:

- expected/desired impacts from the intervention;
- indicators of these impacts;
- sampling frequency;
- equipment required;
- and partners responsible for undertaking the monitoring and coordinating it.

The monitoring plan should be coproduced with the community and partners so that we identify appropriate indicators that are meaningful for all; enrol community members in the monitoring process; and lay the groundwork for generating longer term impact. There is no single right way to do the monitoring. It should reflect what partners want to learn about.

2.6.1.3 Choosing Indicators for monitoring and assessment

Choosing indicators is an important part of developing the monitoring plan. D2.1 gives detailed instructions for the quantitative measurements (e.g. air pollution, noise, traffic speed). The indicators should be meaningful to the stakeholders and, where relevant, consistent across the Labs. Some of the indicators should be obvious from each Lab's data collection plan. Lab teams should define their additional indicators in their implementation plans. (Where relevant, indicators should be adopted from the same frameworks in order to ensure consistency and align current best practice.) There are various indicator frameworks (such as those listed below) that can be drawn upon to monitor interventions. N.B. these frameworks are not exhaustive and partners are free to develop their own indicators as necessary.

CityKeys

<http://www.citykeys-project.eu/>

Funded by the European Union HORIZON 2020 programme, CITYkeys developed and validated, with the aid of cities, key performance indicators and data collection procedures for the common and transparent monitoring as well as the comparability of smart city solutions across European cities

Eclipse

https://ec.europa.eu/research/environment/pdf/renaturing/eklipse_report1_nbs-02022017.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none

Eclipse provides examples of indicators and methods for assessing impacts of Nature Based Solutions that may be applied in a range of different ways across urban areas in Europe. As such, the report also identifies the scale at which the indicators are relevant, to guide an assessment of impacts.

2.6.1.4 Learning

In the relevant table in [Sheet 2.6](#) please list the different stakeholders who may be able to learn from the results of the intervention, and the ways in which their learning will be supported and evaluated.

2.7. Monitoring of interventions

Each intervention should be monitored and reported on in accordance with its monitoring plan as set out in the previous section, and with the questions in [Sheet 2.7](#).

2.8. Lab cycle round-up at the end of the 1st and 2nd Learning Loops

At the end of each learning loop you should sum up the learning that has taken place through the overall process as per the questions in [Sheet 2.8](#) and [Sheet 2.9](#) which are articulated in greater detail below:

- **Who has learned?** (Were all the key actors engaged? To what extent was the learning collective? Was learning shared/transferred among different stakeholders?)
- **What did they learn?** (Was it what they needed to move onto the next step? to participate in collaborative decision-making? to effect change?)
- **How did they learn?** (Which experiences or combination of experiences had most impact? Which activities or tools were most effective?)

3. EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR THE LAB OVERALL

See [Sheet 3.1](#) for the questions to be answered.

3.1 Evaluating Learning around tackled issues

Let's look back at the past learning loop for each issue you tackled. Reflect on the below questions and list your shortcomings, the small and big successes, and any ideas for next time. The below table provides an example. There are eight questions, one for each stage of the learning loop. These questions should be answered by the Lab team.

STAGE OF LEARNING LOOP	EXAMPLE	QUESTIONS FOR EVALUATION
Problem / issue identification.		
Define the scope of the 'wider problem', and the questions to be addressed.	<i>The street light is not working: is it the light bulb, or electrical wiring fault? And it seems many street lights around here are not working.</i>	Does the problem 'frame' fit the problem?
Data gathering		
Decide which information is relevant & gather data, by digital or analogue methods	<i>Is it an old bulb? Is it from the standard supplier? was the light checked last month?</i>	Is the data robust and complete?
Visualisation		
Analyse the data by time or place, or linked factors and causes?	<i>are all the lights broken on the same street? Or from the same supplier? Are there human causes?</i>	Is the analysis suitable and effective?
Analysis		

STAGE OF LEARNING LOOP	EXAMPLE	QUESTIONS FOR EVALUATION
Decide on the specific problem to be solved / resolved	<i>The broken bulb appears to be caused by a low-quality supply / or faulty wiring.</i>	Does the specific problem fit with the 'wider problem'?
Co-design		
Decide / co-design, the most useful response(s), according to the rules and resources available:	<i>e.g. change the bulb / inspect the electric wiring / save for the next cycle of maintenance or renewal.</i>	Are there ways of learning about both specific problems, & wider problems, in order to make better decisions?
Evaluation		
Plan the action for each kind of response:	<i>e.g. send the repair team / contact the residents / order new light bulb / change the supplier, etc.</i>	Are there ways of learning how to plan better?
Implementation		
Manage and complete the actions.	<i>Change the bulb etc.</i>	Are there ways of learning (in the provider organization or supplier), on how to manage this better?
Monitoring & feedback		
Check and monitor the actions, and provide feedback:	<i>Is the light now working? Should we change to a new supplier? Should we change the maintenance cycle?</i>	Are there channels for feedback, to improve the process in the future?

3.2 Assessing the Online Platform

This focuses on the success of the online platform, unforeseen outcomes and implications for setting up similar platforms.

3.3 Community learning on the functional loop: Direct Problem

This focuses on the direct functional problem and the response. For example:

- **information ('know-what')**: did the residents learn about the facts of air pollution and management?
- **networks ('know-who')**: did they learn who to call or ask advice, or to lobby: or who is involved in the service or system?
- **skills and resources ('know-how')**: did they learn the techniques of monitoring and analysis, and project management?
- **norms / goals ('know-why')**: did they learn about environmental health impacts, goals or targets?

3.4 Community learning on the strategic loop: Wider Learning

This focuses on how community learning works, and how much it moves in the direction of community intelligence / empowerment? To address this, we look for:

- **information ('know-what')**: did the residents learn generally about access to technical data and analytical techniques?
- **networks ('know-who')**: did they learn generally who to call or ask advice, or to lobby for similar problems in the local environment?
- **skills and resources ('know-how')**: did they learn general ways of managing information, presenting the results, managing professionals and project management?
- **norms / goals ('know-why')**: did they learn about the general goals of community capacity and empowerment?

3.5 Policy learning on the functional loop

This focuses on functional learning by policymakers.

3.6 Policy learning on the strategic loop

This focuses on strategic learning by policymakers.

3.7 Evaluating the Wider Community and Policy Learning

We aim to understand how and what learning took place due to LOOPER in the wider community.

3.8 Reflect on this Evaluation

This section provides an opportunity to give feedback on the evaluation process.

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ANNEXES

PART 1 - EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH LAB ACTIVITY

Sheet 1.1 - Tracking of the events

Sheet 1.2 - Setting the structure

Sheet 1.3 - Workshop plan

Sheet 1.4 - Post-meeting: participants

Sheet 1.5 - Post-meeting: reflections

Sheet 1.6 - Post-meeting: to-do list

PART 2 - EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

Sheet 2.1 (1st and 2nd loop) - Lab set-up

Sheet 2.2 (1st and 2nd loop) - Scoping

Sheet 2.3 (1st and 2nd loop) - Data collection

Sheet 2.4 (1st and 2nd loop) - Co-Design

Sheet 2.5 (1st and 2nd loop) - Evaluation

Sheet 2.6 (1st and 2nd loop) - Implementation

Sheet 2.7 (1st and 2nd loop) - Monitoring

Sheet 2.8 - 1st Loop

Sheet 2.9 - 2nd Loop

PART 3 - EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR THE LAB OVERALL

Sheet 3.1 - Overall evaluation

PART 1 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH LAB ACTIVITY

SHEET 1.2 – SETTING THE STRUCTURE

INTENTION

What is the intention, or purpose, of the meeting? In other words, why have it?

DESIRED OUTCOME(S)

What specific outcomes should be achieved by the end of the meeting?

AGENDA

What activities will the group go through, in what order, to move toward the desired outcome?

ROLES

What roles or responsibilities need to be in place for the meeting to run smoothly? Who is facilitating, and who is participating? Who is documenting, and who is keeping track of the time? What do you expect of the participants?

RULES

What guidelines will be in place during the meeting? Norms, use of laptops/mobiles, or practical rules related to a space. Let the participants add rules to ensure that they have ownership of them.

TIME

What is the expected time for the meeting, including breaks, and at what time will the meeting end?

PART 1 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
LAB ACTIVITY

SHEET 1.4 – POST-MEETING: PARTICIPANTS

WHY DID YOU COME TODAY?

[...]

HOW DID YOU FEEL WHEN YOU ARRIVED?

[...]

HOW DO YOU FEEL NOW AFTER THE EVENT?

[...]

WHAT WAS SOMETHING NEW THAT YOU LEARNED TODAY?

[...]

WHAT WOULD YOU LIKE MORE INFORMATION ABOUT? IN WHAT FORMAT (online, offline, etc)?

[...]

WHAT WOULD YOU DO DIFFERENTLY NEXT TIME?

[...]

PART 1 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
LAB ACTIVITY

SHEET 1.5 – POST-MEETING: REFLECTIONS

WHAT WE DID

[...]

WHAT WE LEARNED

[...]

WHAT WE ARE GOING TO DO NEXT

[...]

PART 1 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
LAB ACTIVITY

SHEET 1.6 – POST-MEETING: TO-DO LIST

What?	Who?	When?	How?	Done?

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

SHEET 2.1 – LAB SET UP (1ST AND 2ND LOOP)

REFLECTIONS ON SETTING UP THE LAB

HOW DID THE SETTING UP PROCESS WORK?

[...]

COULD IT BE IMPROVED?

[...]

PREPARING TO EVALUATE LEARNING THROUGH THE LOOPER STAGES

WHAT SORT OF LEARNING DO WE NEED TO ACHIEVE LOOPER GOALS OF IMPROVING DECISION MAKING, CO-CREATION AND ADDRESSING PROBLEMS IN THE PUBLIC REALM?

[...]

WHO HAS TO LEARN IN ORDER TO MEET THE LOOPER GOALS OF IMPROVING DECISION MAKING, CO-CREATION AND ADDRESSING PROBLEMS IN THE PUBLIC REALM?

[...]

LEARNING AT EVERY STAGE:

WHO IS MISSING FROM THE ACTIVITIES ASSOCIATED WITH THIS STAGE? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT EFFORTS WERE MADE TO ENGAGE THEM? (both loops)

[...]

WHO IS LEARNING? (both loops)

[...]

HOW WERE THEY ENGAGED? (both loops)

[...]

HOW ARE THEY LEARNING? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT ARE THEY LEARNING? (both loops)

[...]

ARE THERE LESSONS FOR THE NEXT STAGE? (both loops)

[...]

USAGE OF ONLINE TOOLS

WHAT IS THE DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS USING THE ONLINE TOOLS, THE OFFLINE TOOLS OR BOTH TYPES OF TOOLS? (both loops)

[...]

DO ALL PARTICIPANTS HAVE A SMARTPHONE AND INTERNET ACCESS? (both loops)

[...]

HOW EASY TO USE ARE THE ONLINE TOOLS? (both loops)

[...]

HOW DO THE VISUALISATIONS ON THE ONLINE PLATFORM CONTRIBUTE TO THE UNDERSTANDING OF THE ISSUE? (both loops)

[...]

GENERAL MOOD AMONGST LAB PARTICIPANTS

[...]

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

SHEET 2.2 – SCOPING (1ST AND 2ND LOOP)

ENGAGING PEOPLE

WHO IS INVOLVED? (both loops)

[...]

WHO IS NOT INVOLVED? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT DIFFERENCE DOES IT MAKE? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT WORKED AND WHAT DID NOT WORK IN RELATION TO ENGAGING PEOPLE? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT WORKED AND WHAT DID NOT WORK IN RELATION TO IDENTIFYING ISSUES OF CONCERN? (both loops)

[...]

PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

[...]

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

SHEET 2.3 – DATA COLLECTION (1ST AND 2ND LOOP)

PRE-DATA COLLECTION

GIVE EXAMPLES OF COMMENTS BY PARTICIPANTS THAT REFER TO THE DATA, OR THE IMPACT OF THEM COLLECTING THE DATA THEMSELVES (both loops)

[...]

HOW DO PEOPLE TALK ABOUT “PROBLEMS”? WHAT IS *THE* PROBLEM? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT DO PARTICIPANTS USE TO SUPPORT THEIR ARGUMENTS/OPINIONS/IDEAS? (both loops)

[...]

ARE PARTICIPANTS LOOKING FORWARD TO THE DATA COLLECTION? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT HOPES ARE CONNECTED TO IT? (both loops)

[...]

DO THEY TRUST DATA COLLECTED BY OFFICIAL BODIES? WHY OR WHY NOT? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT MAKES THEM WANT TO COLLECT THIS DATA? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT DO THEY HOPE TO DISCOVER? (both loops)

[...]

POST-DATA COLLECTION

NOW THAT THE DATA COLLECTION HAS BEGUN, IS THE STYLE OF DELIBERATION CHANGING? (both loops)

[...]

GIVE EXAMPLES OF COMMENTS BY PARTICIPANTS THAT REFER TO THE DATA, OR THE IMPACT OF THEM COLLECTING THE DATA THEMSELVES? (both loops)

[...]

HOW DO PEOPLE TALK ABOUT PROBLEMS? WHAT IS THE PROBLEM? HAS IT CHANGED OVER TIME? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT DO PARTICIPANTS USE TO SUPPORT THEIR ARGUMENTS/OPINIONS/IDEAS? (both loops)

[...]

DO PARTICIPANTS EFFECTIVELY USE THE COLLECTED DATA AS EVIDENCE TO SUPPORT THEIR ARGUMENTS? OR IS IT DISREGARDED IF IT DOES NOT FIT THEIR WORLDVIEW? (both loops)

[...]

DO THEY TRUST OFFICIAL DATA MORE WHEN THEY CHOOSE WHERE TO MONITOR? (both loops)

WERE THE TOOLS THEY HAD TO COLLECT DATA USER FRIENDLY? IF NOT, HOW COULD THEY BE MORE USER FRIENDLY? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT MADE YOU WANT TO COLLECT THIS DATA? (both loops)

[...]

HOW HAS THE DATA COLLECTED FULFILLED YOUR EXPECTATIONS? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT HAS BEEN CHALLENGING DURING THE DATA COLLECTION? (both loops)

[...]

WHICH DISCOVERIES THROUGH DATA HAVE BEEN HELPFUL? (both loops)

[...]

DO PARTICIPANTS LEARN MORE ABOUT THE ISSUES IDENTIFIED? (both loops)

[...]

DOES IT CHANGE THE OPINIONS ABOUT THE ISSUES? (both loops)

[...]

DOES THE DATA COLLECTED THROUGH THIS MEANS INCREASE CREDIBILITY OF THE FINDINGS AND/OR INTEREST ON THE PART OF STAKEHOLDERS? (both loops)

[...]

HAS IT HELPED TO REDUCE THE CONTRAST BETWEEN CITIZENS AND POLICYMAKERS? (both loops)

[...]

POST-VISUALISATION

WHICH CHALLENGES DID YOU ENCOUNTER WHEN TRYING TO VISUALISE THE COLLECTED DATA? (both loops)

[...]

HOW MUCH DO PEOPLE EFFECTIVELY USE THE VISUALISATION OF THE COLLECTED DATA? (both loops)

[...]

WHICH DATA WAS ACTIVELY LOOKED AT AND DISCUSSED DURING MEETINGS? WHY EXACTLY THIS DATA? (both loops)

[...]

WHICH DATA WAS NOT USED MUCH? WHY WAS THAT? (both loops)

[...]

WAS THE PLATFORM SUFFICIENT IN VISUALISING THE INFORMATION COLLECTED? WHAT WAS MISSING? (both loops)

[...]

DID YOU USE OTHER TOOLS/APPS/PAPER TO COMPLEMENT THE CAPABILITIES OF THE PLATFORM? WHICH ONES AND WHY? (both loops)

[...]

DESCRIBE MOMENTS WHERE PARTICIPANTS GRABBED PEN AND PAPER TO VISUALISE DATA IN DIFFERENT WAYS? (both loops)

[...]

HAS THE DATA CONTRIBUTED TO THE UNDERSTANDING OF THE PROBLEM? IF YES, HOW? (both loops)

[...]

HAS THE TOPIC BECOME MORE PRESENT IN PUBLIC DEBATE OF THE NEIGHBOURHOOD? (both loops)

[...]

HAS THE "NARRATIVE" (typical story of who is good and who is bad and what should be done) CHANGED IN ANY WAY? (both loops)

[...]

IS THE PROBLEM BEING FRAMED DIFFERENTLY IN ANY WAY NOW? (both loops)

[...]

FOR WHICH OF THE DATA COLLECTED WAS THE TIME WELL SPENT? FOR WHICH DATA IS THE RESULT SMALL IN COMPARISON TO THE TIME/COST INVESTED? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED ABOUT HOW CITIZENS PERCEIVE URBAN ISSUES? (both loops)

[...]

DO CITIZENS NEED TO BE PREPARED OR TRAINED BEFORE LETTING THEM DISCUSS VISUALISED DATA? (both loops)

[...]

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

**SHEET 2.4 – CO-DESIGN
(1ST AND 2ND LOOP)**

PRE CO-DESIGN

DESCRIBE THE CO-DESIGN TOOLS YOU ARE USING AND HOW YOU ARE USING THEM.

[...]

HOW AND ON WHAT BASIS DID YOU CHOOSE THESE CO-DESIGN TOOLS?

[...]

LIST AND ADDRESS ANY QUESTIONS YOU HAVE ABOUT SPECIFIC CO-DESIGN TOOLS.

[...]

**WHAT SORT OF OUTREACH DID YOU UNDERTAKE TO ENGAGE PEOPLE WITH THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS
AND HOW SUCCESSFUL WAS IT?**

[...]

**WHO RESPONDED TO THE INVITATION TO PARTICIPATE IN CO-DESIGN? WAS IT A DIFFERENT SET OF
PEOPLE THAN THOSE WHO PARTICIPATED IN EARLIER STAGES? WHAT WAS THE EFFECT OF PREVIOUS
LEVELS OF PARTICIPATION IN LOOPER?**

[...]

WHAT MOTIVATED PEOPLE TO PARTICIPATE IN CO-DESIGN? WHAT WERE THEIR EXPECTATIONS?

[...]

**WHAT PREPARATION DID PARTICIPANTS RECEIVE TO PARTICIPATE IN CO-DESIGN? WHAT SORT OF
INFORMATION WAS PROVIDED TO THEM?**

[...]

POST CO-DESIGN

HOW DID PARTICIPANTS EXPERIENCE THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS? DID THEY ENJOY IT? FIND IT INCLUSIVE? INTIMIDATING/EMPOWERING? WERE THEY SATISFIED WITH THE OUTCOMES?

[...]

WHAT FEEDBACK DID THEY PROVIDE CONCERNING DIFFERENT CO-DESIGN TOOLS?

[...]

WAS THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS ENRICHED BY THE PARTICIPATION OF DIFFERENT ACTORS? IN WHAT WAY? (both loops)

[...]

WERE THE PROPOSALS MORE DIVERSE? MORE CREATIVE? BETTER DEVELOPED? BETTER ADAPTED? MORE WIDELY SUPPORTED? (both loops)

[...]

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

SHEET 2.5 – EVALUATION OF POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS (1ST AND 2ND LOOP)

PRE EVALUATION OF POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

DESCRIBE HOW MCA OR MAMCA WAS USED IN YOUR LAB. WAS IT AN ONLINE EXERCISE OR A WORKSHOP OR BOTH?

[...]

WHO WAS INVITED TO PARTICIPATE IN THE MCA OR MAMCA PROCESS? WHAT IS THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO THE LOOPER LAB? HOW WERE THEY SELECTED?

[...]

WHAT WERE THE PARTICIPANTS ASKED TO DO?

[...]

WHAT SORT OF INFORMATION WERE THE PARTICIPANTS PRESENTED WITH ABOUT THE MCA/MAMCA PROCESS AND ABOUT THE PREVIOUS STAGES OF LOOPER?

[...]

HOW DID THE PARTICIPANTS EXPERIENCE PREPARING TO PARTICIPATE IN THE MCA/MAMCA PROCESS?

[...]

POST EVALUATION OF POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

HOW DID YOU FEEL ABOUT OUR EVALUATION TOOL/GAME (MAMCA)? (both loops)

[...]

DID IT ENRICH THE SUBSEQUENT DEBATE? (both loops)

[...]

HOW DID IT HELP THE GROUP IN REACHING A DECISION? (both loops)

[...]

WERE PARTICIPANTS SATISFIED WITH THE FINAL OUTCOME? (DID THEY AGREE WITH IT? DID THEY THINK IT PROVIDED VALUE ADDED TO THE LOOPER PROCESS?)

[...]

WHAT WAS THE NATURE OF THE INTERACTION AMONG NEW AND PREVIOUS PARTICIPANTS; AMONG RESIDENTS AND INSTITUTIONAL PARTICIPANTS?

[...]

DID PARTICIPATION IN THE MCA/MAMCA PROCESS SERVE TO ENGAGE NEW PARTNERS OR INCREASE ENGAGEMENT OF EXISTING ONES? IF SO, HOW WAS THIS DEMONSTRATED?

[...]

DID PARTICIPANTS IN MCA/MAMCA GET INVOLVED IN SUBSEQUENT LOOPER ACTIVITIES OR FOLLOW UP? WHAT ARE EXAMPLES OF THIS?

[...]

WHAT HAVE WE LEARNED ABOUT HOW MCA/MAMCA CAN BE EFFECTIVELY COMBINED WITH PARTICIPATORY DATA COLLECTION AND CO-DESIGN?

[...]

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

SHEET 2.6 – IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERVENTIONS AND MONITORING PLANS (1ST AND 2ND LOOP)

PRE IMPLEMENTATION

INTERVENTION		
Title	Photo	100 word summary

WHAT IS THE INTERVENTION? (both loops)

[...]

WHERE IS IT? (both loops)

[...]

HOW LARGE AN AREA DOES IT COVER? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT IS THE DURATION OF THE EXPERIMENT? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT PROBLEMS DOES IT RESPOND TO? (both loops)

[...]

HOW/WHY WAS THIS INTERVENTION CHOSEN? (both loops)

[...]

HOW MUCH FUNDING IS REQUIRED? (both loops)

[...]

PARTNER DETAILS

Partner name	Role in intervention	Funded/in-kind contribution

EXPECTED IMPACT? (both loops)

[...]

INDICATOR? (both loops)

[...]

MONITORING FRAMEWORK? (both loops)

[...]

RESPONSIBILITY? (both loops)

[...]

LEARNING

Stakeholder	Intended learning	Method to support learning	Evaluation of learning

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

SHEET 2.7 – MONITORING OF INTERVENTIONS (1ST AND 2ND LOOP)

WHICH ACTORS ARE INVOLVED IN THE ACTUAL IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SOLUTION? (both loops)

[...]

HOW ARE THESE ACTORS INVOLVED? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT DIFFERENCE DOES THEIR PARTICIPATION MAKE TO THEIR LEARNING? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT DIFFERENCE DOES THEIR PARTICIPATION MAKE TO THE INTERVENTION? (both loops)

[...]

WHAT DIFFERENCE DOES THEIR PARTICIPATION MAKE TO THE FOLLOW UP? (both loops)

[...]

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

SHEET 2.8 – END OF 1ST LEARNING LOOP

WHO HAS LEARNED?

[...]

WHAT DID THEY LEARN?

[...]

HOW DID THEY LEARN?

[...]

**WHAT GUIDELINES OR RECOMMENDATIONS SHOULD BE SHARED WITH PEOPLE INTERESTED IN
UNDERTAKING A SIMILAR PROCESS?**

[...]

PART 2 – EVALUATION TASKS AND QUESTIONS FOR EACH
STAGE OF THE LAB CYCLE

SHEET 2.9 – END OF 2ND LEARNING LOOP

WHO HAS LEARNED?

[...]

WHAT DID THEY LEARN?

[...]

HOW DID THEY LEARN?

[...]

**WHAT GUIDELINES OR RECOMMENDATIONS SHOULD BE SHARED WITH PEOPLE INTERESTED IN
UNDERTAKING A SIMILAR PROCESS?**

[...]

AT THE END OF THE SECOND LOOP - GENERAL

WHAT MODIFICATIONS WERE MADE TO THE INTERVENTION?

[...]

WHAT MODIFICATIONS WERE MADE TO THE LAB ITSELF?

[...]

SHEET 3.1 – OVERALL EVALUATION

REFLECTING ON THE OVERALL LAB PROCESS: EVALUATING LEARNING AROUND TACKLED ISSUES

HOW DID THE PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION GO? DOES THE PROBLEM “FRAME” FIT THE PROBLEM?

[...]

HOW DID THE DATA GATHERING GO? IS THE DATA ROBUST AND COMPLETE?

[...]

HOW DID THE DATA VISUALISATION GO? IS THE ANALYSIS SUITABLE AND EFFECTIVE?

[...]

HOW DID THE PROBLEM ANALYSIS GO? DOES THE SPECIFIC PROBLEM FIT WITH THE “WIDER PROBLEM”?

[...]

HOW DID THE CO-DESIGN GO? ARE THERE WAYS OF LEARNING ABOUT BOTH SPECIFIC PROBLEMS AND WIDER PROBLEMS, IN ORDER TO MAKE BETTER DECISIONS?

[...]

HOW DID THE EVALUATION GO? ARE THERE WAYS OF IMPROVING GROUP DECISION-MAKING?

[...]

HOW DID THE SOLUTION IMPLEMENTATION GO? ARE THERE WAYS OF LEARNING HOW TO PLAN BETTER? ARE THERE WAYS OF LEARNING (IN THE PROVIDER ORGANIZATION OR SUPPLIER) ON HOW TO MANAGE THIS BETTER?

[...]

HOW DID THE MONITORING AND FEEDBACK GO? ARE THERE CHANNELS FOR FEEDBACK, TO IMPROVE

THE PROCESS IN THE FUTURE?

[...]

ONLINE PLATFORM

DID THE TECHNICAL PLATFORM WORK AS INTENDED?

[...]

WERE THERE PROBLEMS OR GAPS?

[...]

DID IT PRODUCE NEGATIVE SIDE-EFFECTS?

[...]

DID IT PRODUCE POSITIVE SPIN-OFFS?

[...]

WAS THERE AN EFFECTIVE OFFLINE/SOCIAL PLATFORM?

[...]

WHAT ARE THE IMPLICATIONS FOR OTHERS SETTING UP SIMILAR PLATFORMS?

[...]

COMMUNITY LEARNING ON THE FUNCTIONAL LOOP: DIRECT PROBLEM

INFORMATION (KNOW-WHAT)

[...]

NETWORKS (KNOW-WHO)

[...]

SKILLS AND RESOURCES (KNOW-HOW)

[...]

NORMS/GOALS (KNOW-WHY)

[...]

COMMUNITY LEARNING ON THE STRATEGIC LOOP: WIDER LEARNING

INFORMATION (KNOW-WHAT)

[...]

NETWORKS (KNOW-WHO)

[...]

SKILLS AND RESOURCES (KNOW-HOW)

[...]

NORMS/GOALS (KNOW-WHY)

[...]

POLICY LEARNING ON THE FUNCTIONAL LOOP

TO WHAT DEGREE DID POLICY-MAKERS LEARN NEW INFORMATION ON THE LOCAL PROBLEMS OF AIR QUALITY AND AIR MANAGEMENT?

[...]

DID POLICY-MAKERS LEARN WHO TO CALL (IN THE COMMUNITY), OR ASK FOR ADVICE, OR TO CONSULT?

[...]

DID POLICY-MAKERS LEARN MORE ABOUT THE TECHNIQUES OF PARTICIPATORY CITIZEN MONITORING AND ANALYSIS, AND CITIZEN CO-DESIGN IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT?

[...]

DID POLICY-MAKERS LEARN MORE ABOUT THE TARGETS AND THRESHOLDS OF ENVIRONMENTAL HEALTH POLICY?

[...]

POLICY LEARNING ON THE STRATEGIC LOOP

WHAT DID THE POLICY-MAKERS LEARN GENERALLY ABOUT IMPROVING ACCESS TO TECHNICAL DATA AND ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES?

[...]

WHAT DID POLICY-MAKERS LEARN GENERALLY ON WHO TO INVOLVE IN THE COMMUNITY OR ON OTHER STAKEHOLDERS IN THE LOCAL ENVIRONMENT?

[...]

WHAT DID THE POLICY-MAKERS LEARN GENERALLY ON THE WAYS OF MANAGING PARTICIPATION, BUILDING IT INTO POLICY DEVELOPMENT AND CO-DESIGN OF INTERVENTIONS?

[...]

WHAT DID POLICY MAKERS LEARN ABOUT THE GENERAL GOALS OF COMMUNITY CAPACITY AND LOCAL EMPOWERMENT?

[...]

EVALUATING THE WIDER COMMUNITY AND POLICY LEARNING

DID THE CAPACITY BUILDING PROCESS WORKING? WAS IT OPEN AND INCLUSIVE FOR ALL SOCIAL GROUPS?

[...]

DID THE CO-DESIGN PROCESS WORK EFFECTIVELY? WERE ALL VIABLE OPTIONS ON THE TABLE? WAS THERE A ROBUST PROCESS OF DECISION MAKING?

[...]

WHAT IS THE EVIDENCE OF COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT? CAN IT BE ASSESSED IN ACTIVITIES, RELATIONS, COMMUNICATIONS, POSITIVE ACTIONS?

[...]

DO THE POLICY AND SERVICE PROVIDERS HAVE THE RESOURCES TO ADDRESS THE PROBLEM? OR CAN THEY LEARN HOW TO GATHER AND MOBILIZE THE RESOURCES?

[...]

IS POLICY DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION WORKING EFFECTIVELY? IS IT (AS FAR AS POSSIBLE) OPEN, TRANSPARENT, INCLUSIVE, ENTERPRENEURIAL AND CREATIVE?

[...]

IS THERE A FORMAL EVALUATION PROCESS? IS THERE AN EMBEDDED CULTURE OF OPEN DEBATE AND EVALUATION?

[...]

REFLECT ON THIS EVALUATION PROCESS

HOW DID YOU EXPERIENCE THIS EVALUATION PROCESS?

[...]

WAS THE EVALUATION PROCESS EFFECTIVE AND USEFUL?

[...]

WHAT ARE ITS SHORTCOMINGS AND STRENGTHS?

[...]

HOW COULD IT BE IMPROVED FOR OTHER PROJECTS?

[...]